

Indirect Speech, Interrogative Indirect Speech (In the Example of Uzbek and French Languages)

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the ways of expressing someone else's speech in Uzbek and French, which is one of the important areas of the category of communicative purpose, and its simple technique, indirect speech. It focuses on the textual features of indirect speech (le discours indirect) and interrogative indirect speech. At the same time, the functional and semantic features of other types of speech in two languages are explained.*

Key words: *someone else's speech, indirect speech, interrogative indirect speech, speech verb, quotation mark, hyphen, colon, tense agreement.*

Introduction. The phenomenon of foreign speech is one of the important areas of the category of communicative purpose in modern linguistics. The speaker not only expresses his opinion all the time, but sometimes uses other people's words in his speech. On this basis, another special type of complex sentence is formed. The person expressing the speech of another is the author, and his speech is called the author's speech. The author's presentation of the opinion of a certain person in his speech is the speech of another, and the speaker (other) is considered to be the person whose speech is expressed. When expressing foreign-language speech, the speaker expresses not his own opinion about the essence, but the opinion or conversation of others.

The main part. The phenomenon of foreign speech, which is one of the important directions of the category of communicative purpose, is one of the directions that has its place in modern linguistics. Foreign speech is divided into 3 types and is formed as a communication event. These are [1, 254]:

- 1) direct speech (le discours direct)
- 2) indirect speech (le discours indirect)
- 3) Non-one registering speech (le discours indirect libre)

In direct speech, the speech of another person is conveyed to the listener without changing its form and content. When there is no need to give the speaker's speech verbatim, a passive sentence is used. Sometimes the other person's speech is between a derived sentence and a possessive sentence. In this case, the other person's opinion is expressed without the participation of the author-speaker, that is, the author acts as the speaker in the quoted sentence. That's why such sentences are considered to be non-self-excerpted sentences [5, 294]. This type of foreign speech is unique to fiction, and when added to the author's text, it expresses the thoughts and feelings of the heroes of the work, and serves to reveal their inner world.

The second important method of expression of foreign speech is that the syntactic structure of the speech is radically changed in the case of acquired speech, in contrast to the extracted message. It has several unique grammatical features:

1) in the Uzbek language, a possessive sentence formed syntactically is a sentence that is simple in form and complex in content, while in French, such sentences are in the form of a complementing clause;

2) in French, the following conjunction (que, si, de...) is used;

3) the form of the person changes (usually the third person).

Assimilation is formed in a syntactic and morphological way. Among the compared languages, morphological acquisition is characteristic only of the Uzbek literary language, and in French there is only the first type of acquisition, that is, syntactic acquisition.

Acquisition in Uzbek is expressed in two ways: one is syntactic, the other is morphological. The smallest form of assimilation formed by syntactic means is made by adding two stems, suffixes or auxiliary words to the base. In the Uzbek language, assimilation formed morphologically has three types of content: 1) assimilation command, 2) assimilation message (desire, etc.), 3) assimilation word rock.

METHODS

In the Uzbek language, the following tools are used to express the meaning of a passive message (wish, etc.), passive command, passive interrogative: *-(i)bdi, -adi (-ydi), -gan, -gan ekan, -gan emish, -(a)r ekan, -(a)r emish, -(a)yotgan ekan, -(a)yot-gan emish, -adigan (-ydigan) ekan, -adigan (-ydigan) emish, -moqchi ekan, -moqchi emish, -sin ekan, -sin emish* forms as well as nouns and other word groups, *ekan, emish* incomplete verb, etc.:

O'g'lim aytdi, do'stlari bilan gaplashibdi.

Oyim aytdilar, darsingni qilar ekansan.

O'qituvchi so'rayapti, o'quvchilar musobaqaga qatnashar ekanmi?

These tools represent a native command, native message, and native question in speech and microtext.

Unlike the Uzbek language, acquisition in French is carried out only syntactically. From the point of view of syntax, the possessive clause corresponds to the complementary subordinate clause, and the tenses in such a compound sentence are adapted. The possessive sentence is in the form of a statement, command and question [2, 227, 228].

Self-directed speech is another way of transmitting speech to another person. In doing so, it grammatically adapts to the author's speech. The spoken sentence is usually formed as a subordinate clause of the speech verb contained in the author's sentence (for example, *dire-to say, s'écrier-to shout, demander-to ask, exiger-to demand, etc.*) and the following conjunction is formed. will be In this case, if the author's speech fulfills the function of the main clause, the said sentence comes as a subordinate clause, and they are connected with the conjunction *que* and *si, de*, and other lexical units that act as conjunctions.

In French, conjunction selection, tense and person adaptations are one of the important aspects of acquired speech.

Lexical units (*que, si, de*) in the function of different connectors are used depending on the type of spoken speech:

- 1) the conjunction "que" (*qu'* before the words beginning with letters *a, e, и, o, u, y* and *x*) is used when pronouns and exclamatory sentences are given as possessive clauses:
- *Le journaliste dit que'il y a une manifestation contre la réforme.*
- 2) in French, an imperative sentence is converted into a possessive sentence in two ways. One of them comes in the form of a simple sentence and the command part of the sentence spoken in it takes the form of "de" + infinitive from the main verb, and the other takes the form of a complementary subordinate clause with a subjunctive.

- Il m'a dit de faire ce rapport-là.
- Il m'a dit que je fasse ce rapport-là.
- 3) Interrogative sentences can be connected to the main sentence by means of different words depending on the question given to the part of the sentence.
- a) when interrogative sentences without an interrogative word and made with the phrase est-ce que are acquired, the conjunction si/s' (before il or ils) is used:
 - Il demande si tu aimes Paris.
 - Le journaliste demande s'il y a une manifestation contre la réforme.
- b) when the subject is asked a question in an interrogative possessive sentence, it is connected to the main sentence by means of the conjunction si:
 - "Fait-il chaud?" a demandé Anwar.
 - Anwar a demandé s'il faisait chaud.
- c) when a question is asked to a possessive and passive complement in an interrogative possessive sentence, they are expressed as follows:
 - • a possessive or indirect complement expressed by a person is connected to the main clause by the interrogative word qui:
 - « Who is in service? » a-t-il demandé.
 - Il a demandé qui était de service.
 - Oziza m'a demandé : « Qui as-tu rencontré? »
 - Elle m'a demandé qui j'avais rencontré.
 - • the possessive or passive complement represented by the subject is connected to the main clause by the words ce qui, ce que:
 - Mon ami m'a demandé : « Qu'est-ce qui t'inquiète ? »
 - Elle m'a demandé ce qui m'inquiétait.
 - Farkhod leur a demandé : « Que ferez-vous demain ? »
 - Farkhod leur a demandé ce qu'ils feraient demain.
 - • an instrumental complement represented by a person is connected to the main clause by the interrogative word qui used with a preposition:
 - Akbar asked me: "A qui pensez-vous?" »
 - Il m'a demandé à qui je pensais.
 - Talib a demandé : « De qui parle-t-il ? »
 - Talib a demandé de qui il parlait.
 - • the instrumental complement represented by the subject is connected to the main clause through the interrogative word quoi used with a preposition:
 - Abror m'a demandé: « A quoi penses-tu? »
 - Abror m'a demandé à quoi je pensais.
 - Chavkat a demandé : « Avec quoi écrivez-vous ? »
 - Chavkat lui a demandé avec quoi il écrivait.
 - • the determining clause expressed by a person and an object is connected with the interrogative word quel:

J'ai demandé à mes amis : « Quel film avez-vous vu ? »

*Je leur ai demandé **quel** film ils avaient vu.*

*Mon ami a demandé : “ **Quelle** délégation est arrivée ? »*

*Mon ami a demandé **quelle** délégation était arrivée.*

- the interrogative in the possessive sentence is connected with the interrogative word in the derived sentence, that is, the interrogative word remains unchanged:

Elle a demandé à son amie : « Quand tes parents sont-ils arrivés ? Où sont-ils à présent? Comment vont-ils?»

Elle a demandé à son amie quand ses parents étaient arrivés, où ils étaient et comment ils allaient.

- when interrogative sentences with interrogative words are mastered, the interrogative word is used as a connector:

Le journaliste demande où/quand/pourquoi il y a une manifestation contre la réforme.

CONCLUSION

Assimilation is formed in a syntactic and morphological way. Mastery of the Uzbek language is expressed in two ways. The smallest form of assimilation formed by syntactic means is made by adding two stems, suffixes or auxiliary words to the base. In the Uzbek language, assimilation formed morphologically has three types of content: 1) assimilation command, 2) assimilation message (desire, etc.), 3) assimilation word rock

In the French language, the phenomenon of assimilation is carried out syntactically. From the point of view of syntax, the possessive clause corresponds to the complement clause and grammatically adapts to the author's speech. The spoken sentence is usually formed as a subordinate part of the speech verb contained in the author's sentence (for example, dire-to say, s'écrier-to shout, demander-to ask, exiger-to demand, etc.) and the following compound sentence is formed. In French, the choice of connectives, tense and person adaptations are one of the important aspects of acquired speech.

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